

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE CONCEPTS OF ACQUISITION AND LEARNING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES LIES IN THEIR APPROACHES AND PROCESSES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14879933>

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Annotation. This article explores the distinction between language acquisition and language learning, emphasizing their different processes and roles in second language development. It reviews key theories, particularly Krashen's hypothesis, which highlights the unconscious, natural process of language acquisition in contrast to the conscious, formal process of language learning. The article further examines the impact of affective variables, such as motivation, self-confidence, and anxiety, on second language acquisition. It also discusses how these factors influence language proficiency and achievement. Through a comprehensive review of research, the article illustrates the importance of understanding these distinctions for educators and language learners. The relationship between language acquisition and learning strategies is explored, with a focus on how learners' characteristics, experiences, and educational background affect their language learning outcomes. Overall, the article suggests that recognizing the differences between acquisition and learning can enhance teaching methods and improve learner outcomes in second language.

Аннотация. В этой статье исследуются различия между овладением языком и изучением языка, подчеркиваются их различные процессы и роли в развитии второго языка. В нем рассматриваются ключевые теории, в частности гипотеза Крашена, которая подчеркивает бессознательный, естественный процесс овладения языком в отличие от сознательного, формального процесса изучения языка. В статье дополнительно исследуется влияние аффективных переменных, таких как мотивация, уверенность в себе и тревога, на овладение вторым языком. В нем также обсуждается, как эти факторы влияют на знание языка и успеваемость. Благодаря всестороннему обзору исследований статья иллюстрирует важность понимания этих различий для преподавателей и изучающих язык. Исследуется взаимосвязь между овладением языком и стратегиями обучения с акцентом на то, как характеристики, опыт и образование учащихся влияют на результаты их изучения языка. В целом, статья предполагает, что признание различий между приобретением и обучением может улучшить методы обучения и улучшить результаты обучения на втором языке.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola tilni o'zlashtirish va til o'rganish o'rtasidagi farqni o'rganadi va ularning ikkinchi tilni rivojlantirishdagi turli jarayonlari va rollarini ta'kidlaydi. U asosiy nazariyalarni, xususan, til o'rganishning ongli, rasmiy jarayonidan farqli o'laroq, tilni o'zlashtirishning ongsiz, tabiiy jarayonini ta'kidlaydigan Krashen gipotezasini ko'rib chiqadi. Maqolada motivatsiya, o'ziga ishonch va tashvish kabi affektiv o'zgaruvchilarning ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirishga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, ushbu omillar tilni bilish va muvaffaqiyatga qanday ta'sir qilishini muhokama qiladi. Tadqiqotni har tomonlama ko'rib chiqish orqali maqola o'qituvchilar va til o'rganuvchilar uchun ushbu farqlarni tushunish muhimligini ko'rsatadi. Tilni o'zlashtirish va o'rganish strategiyalari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik o'rganilib, asosiy e'tibor o'quvchilarning xususiyatlari, tajribasi va ta'lim darajasi ularning til o'rganish natijalariga qanday ta'sir qilishiga qaratilgan. Umuman olganda, maqolada o'zlashtirish va o'rganish o'rtasidagi farqlarni tan olish o'qitish usullarini yaxshilash va ikkinchi tilda o'quvchilar natijalarini yaxshilash mumkin.

Key words: *concept, acquisition, perspectives, interconnection, conscious, methodology, subconscious, contradiction.*

Ключевые слова: *понятие, приобретение, перспективы, взаимосвязь, сознание, методология, подсознание, противоречие.*

Tayanch soʻzlar: *tushuncha, egallash, istiqbol, oʻzaro bogʻliqlik, ongli, metodologiya, ong osti, ziddiyat.*

Language is considered one of the most crucial tools for conveying ideas to others. The process of language acquisition remains a captivating aspect of human development. From early monosyllabic expressions to the use of complex, nuanced, and context-sensitive structures, both the stages of progress and the methods of language acquisition have been central to countless studies in evolutionary linguistics, psychology, and pedagogy. The ability to use two or more languages enables individuals to create diverse, integrated networks that facilitate new learning experiences.

According to Krashen, acquiring communication skills involves learning a language in the same way children acquire their mother tongue—naturally and without conscious focus on the language system. In contrast, learning a language involves deliberate attention to its formal structure and rules. Additionally, fundamental factors such as cognitive and environmental aspects are believed to influence both first and second language acquisition.

The contemporary challenges of global evolutionary trends highlight the critical importance of sustainable development, defined as “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”¹ This concept reflects an individual’s readiness to adapt both external and internal perspectives, making these elements crucial for the development of a stable identity. Consequently, the necessity to harmonize external and internal frameworks informs the research methodology examining the interplay between language acquisition and learning within pedagogical discourse, as illustrated by Ahrens² in figure: 1. Analyzing the two syntheses reveals differences between external and internal perspectives, particularly in how they relate to the learners’ conditions. External perspectives often emphasize learners’ conscious, systematic approaches to studying a language. The accompanying figure further illustrates the shifts in synthesis.

Figure 1. Development of external and internal perspectives as a life necessity

¹ Robbins, D. (2007) Vygotsky’s and Leontiev’s Non-classical Psychology Related to Second Language Acquisition. International Nordic-Baltic Region Conference of FIPLV Innovations in Language Teaching and Learning in the Multicultural Context 15-16th June, 2007, Riga, Latvia.

² Cohen, A.D. & Scott, K., 1996: A synthesis of approaches to assessing language learning strategies. In R. Oxford (Ed.), Language Learning Strategies Around the World: Cross-cultural Perspectives (pp. 89-106). Manoa: University of Hawaii Press.

In real-life experiences, it is often observed that a capable individual is understood from one of two perspectives: either through internal potentials, which focus on cognition, or through external perspectives, which emphasize social connections and highlight the balance between these two viewpoints. Therefore, the most appropriate suggestion in this context is the welfare outcome rooted in the essential requirement of dialogue between two individuals. Exploring the relationship between language acquisition and language learning involves examining the influence of key concepts such as “language acquisition,” “language learning,” “mother tongue,” and “foreign language.” This approach sheds light on how these fundamental ideas shape and impact both external and internal developmental systems.

At the initial stage, the perception of the native language occurs through spontaneous, free communication. Over time, it evolves into a more conscious form with linguistic structure. In contrast, the development of a foreign or second language begins consciously and then gradually becomes more spontaneous. To clarify, we start communicating in our mother tongue spontaneously and later learn its formal aspects, whereas foreign languages begin as formal and later become spontaneous in use. Therefore, the discussion of spontaneous, academic, and professional languages relates to the concepts of native, foreign, and professional languages. Specifically, professional language is a type of native language learned for specific purposes. In this regard, the research community emphasizes that the relationship between language acquisition and language learning plays a crucial role in development. “Scientific and spontaneous learning concepts are distinctly different, but in some teaching and learning processes, they overlap.” Consequently, the prominence of spontaneous learning indicates an individual’s current development level, while the extent of academic learning reflects the individual's nearest zone of growth, according to Vygotsky’s Theory of the Proximal Zone of Development.³

The distinction between acquisition and learning is arguably one of the most fundamental hypotheses ever presented. It suggests that adults have two distinct and independent methods for developing proficiency in a second language. The first method is language acquisition, which mirrors the process by which children develop skills in their first language. Generally, we unconsciously understand the rules of the language we acquire. Instead of consciously knowing these rules, we have an “intuition” for correct language usage. Grammatical structures “sound” right, and when they are incorrect, we instinctively sense that something is wrong, even if we cannot explicitly identify the grammatical rule involved. This process also includes other forms of language development, such as informal learning, implicit language acquisition, and natural language learning.

The second way to develop competence in a second language is through learning. The term “learning” typically refers to a conscious process where learners are aware of grammar rules, formal language, and are able to understand and apply them as needed. In simple terms, learning is the “knowledge about” languages, often referred to by many people as “grammar” or “rules.” Some synonyms for this include formal language knowledge and explicit learning.

It should be noted that some second language theorists believe children acquire languages naturally, while adults can only learn them. However, the learning/acquisition hypothesis argues that adults also have the ability to acquire languages and that the capacity to “pick up” languages does not disappear with adulthood. This does not mean that adults will always reach native-like proficiency in a second or foreign language, but it suggests that adults have access to the same “language acquisition devices” that children use. As we will see later, language acquisition remains a crucial process for adults.

While error correction has little or no effect on subconscious acquisition, it is believed to be beneficial for conscious learning. Correcting mistakes helps learners understand or “sort out”

³ Vygotsky, L. (1934/1962) *Thought and Language. The Development of Scientific Concepts in Childhood* Cambridge, MS: MIT.

the necessary grammatical rules. For example, if an English language learner says, "I do my homework every day," and the teacher corrects the sentence by repeating it correctly, the learner is expected to realize that the "s" ending applies to the third person singular and not the first person, thereby adjusting their conscious understanding of the rule. This seems logical, but it is unclear whether error correction has this effect in practice.

Research on children's language acquisition suggests that error correction does not significantly impact language acquisition. Brown and his colleagues found that adults typically correct only minor aspects of a child's language, such as occasional pronunciation issues, verb errors, or inappropriate language. These studies suggest that parents focus more on the content of what the child is saying rather than its form. For example, Brown and Beluga⁴ note that when a child says, "Mother curl my hair," the correction is often minimal because the mother is actually curling the child's hair, emphasizing the meaning over the grammatical structure.

On the other hand, the sentence "Walt Disney come on Tuesday" was corrected for its syntactic accuracy because, in reality, Walt Disney appeared on TV on Monday. Brown concludes that it is often the "correct value" or the meaningful identity that guides explicit verbal reinforcement by parents, rather than the syntactic correctness. This creates a paradox, as the typical outcome of this approach is an adult whose speaking skills are well-structured but not necessarily grammatically accurate⁵. The distinction between acquisition and learning may not be unique to second language acquisition. Indeed, we "learn" certain aspects of our first language in schools, and a similar distinction has been made in other domains.

In a grammatical syllabus, each structure is introduced only once. If a student misses the lesson, is absent, or doesn't pay attention, or if there isn't enough input, the student may have to wait until the following year when the structures are revisited. On the other hand, more flexible input allows for natural review and reinforcement.

A grammatical syllabus assumes that we can predict the order of language acquisition. However, scholar Krashen argues that such an assumption is unnecessary, emphasizing instead the reliance on input, particularly through naturally occurring, roughly tuned native communication. Research conducted over the years has shown that a variety of affective factors contribute to success in second language acquisition. Most of these factors can be grouped into three categories:

1. **Motivation:** Highly motivated learners generally perform better in second language acquisition, often driven by "integrative" motivation (though not always). This is why it is important to encourage learners through various activities.

2. **Self-confidence:** Self-confidence plays a significant role in all areas, including second language performance. Teachers should focus on boosting learners' confidence and fostering learner autonomy.

3. **Anxiety:** Low anxiety is beneficial for second language acquisition, whether it is individual or classroom anxiety. In some cases, attitudinal factors are more closely related to acquisition than to learning, and they tend to show stronger connections with language development when speech-based tests are used. These tests tap into the needed language systems rather than the accepted ones, and when students use the language in "acquisition" situations where comprehensible input is abundant.

As previously mentioned, earlier research methods focused on identifying strategic approaches and characteristics that distinguish language acquisition from learning. However, more recent studies have aimed to explore language learning behaviors and classify the strategies used by language learners during the learning process. Additionally, a wealth of research has

⁴ Vygotsky, L. (1934/1962) *Thought and Language. The Development of Scientific Concepts in Childhood* Cambridge, MS: MIT

⁵ Vygotsky, L. (1934/1962) *Thought and Language. The Development of Scientific Concepts in Childhood* Cambridge, MS: MIT

shown that there is a connection between the use and selection of learning strategies and various contextual factors such as learner characteristics, experiences, language proficiency, and educational background. Researchers have concluded that understanding the differences between acquisition and learning helps to enhance and develop learners' knowledge in various ways. It is also suggested that there is a close relationship between language proficiency and achievement in language learning.

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